

How to Create Photos That Tell Stories and Make an Impact

Join the course

Visual Storytelling

Neil Bennett

Tim Winkler

When?

April 23 and 29

🕒 11:00

Photographing Belonging: Everyday Stories from a Ukrainian University Without Walls

Short abstract

This visual album presents a curated collection of photographs and accompanying narratives created by students and staff of Berdyansk State Pedagogical University during an online visual storytelling course organized in collaboration with Future Campus. Developed in the context of war, displacement, and the loss of a shared physical campus, the project invited participants to document fragments of their everyday lives through images and short reflective texts.

Kateryna
Bukhtiarova

For me, language is more than just a means of communication. I am learning to feel a word: its precision, its sound, its power. In books, I find answers; in texts, I find myself; and in every line, I discover new meanings.

I am learning not only to write and analyze, but also to listen, understand, and convey emotions through words. To be a philologist is to love one's native language, to search for truth, and to constantly discover something new. It is a part of who I am and the path I have chosen.

Natalia
Romanova

Lviv. Opera House. Summer Evening

August 2, 2023, 21:56

The Lviv National Academic Opera and Ballet Theater named after Solomiya Krushelnytska is an opera and ballet theater in Lviv, in the historical center of the city, at Svobody Avenue, 28. Named in honor of the famous Ukrainian opera singer Solomiya Krushelnytska.

Natalia
Romanova

Lviv. Bernardine Monastery and St. Andrew's Church

October 5, 2025, 7:23 PM

This is one of the oldest church complexes in Lviv, the construction of which began at the end of the 15th century. The Bernardine Monastery for a long time served as an external defensive outpost, since it was located outside the city walls.

The Church of St. Andrew was built at the turn of the 17th–18th centuries. under the leadership of different architects and under the influence of different styles. By Pavel Rymlyanyn in the Renaissance, Ambrose Prikhylny in Mannerism, and was completed by Andreas Boehmer in the Baroque style.

The interior of the church is special, striking in its abundance of Baroque ornaments and gilding; it was decorated with frescoes by the monk Benedikt Mazurkevych in 1738–1740.

In 1784, the Austrian authorities established the "Archive of City and Zemstvo Acts of the City of Lviv" in the monastery's cells. The modern Central State Historical Archive is the largest in Ukraine.

Today, the Church of St. Andrew the First-Called is an active Greek Catholic church.

Natalia
Romanova

Ostroh (Rivne region). Alley of the park named after T. G. Shevchenko

March 4, 2024, 18:54

The photo was taken in the evening, when the spring sun begins to set.

Natalia
Romanova

Ostroh (Rivne region). Round tower of the 16th century

May 11, 2024

The New (Round) Tower (tower) in Ostroh, Rivne region is a landmark of defensive architecture of the 16th century, located on Akademichna Street, 5. It was part of the fortifications of the Ostroh Castle, which belonged to the Ostroh princes.

Features: It is one of the oldest round towers-dungeons that has survived to this day, and is part of a complex that demonstrates the grandeur of the city-residence of princes.

Natalia
Romanova

Ostroh (Rivne region). Independence Ave. Sunset

March 28, 2024

Natalia
Romanova

Ostroh (Rivne region). Reliable alarm system

September 15, 2025

The owner of the dog entered the store, and the dog guards the vehicle.

Karyna
Vasylieva

Spring in Zaporizhzhia

Nature is not disturbed by shelling — it quietly continues to live, bloom, and breathe, as if reminding us that life is stronger than any noise of war. And the city stubbornly keeps its rhythm — in constant motion, in familiar routes and streets. And all that remains for us is memory, which preserves more than words ever can.

Anton
Serdiuchenko

I thought the task would be easier, but it wasn't.

Storm

April 26, 2026

Feels like a screenshot from Stranger Things for me 😊

Anton
Serdiuchenko

A couple of old photos I took in Berdiansk before 2022.

Sunset

June 14, 2021

A definition of “the good old days”. The last free summer in Berdiansk.

Anton
Serdiuchenko

Thunderstorm

March 2021

My personal battle between fear of being struck by lightning and learning about long exposure.

Anton
Serdiuchenko

Cat

July 23, 2020

Cats don't need explanation 😊

Anton
Serdiuchenko

Photo from my home village:

Village

April 27, 2025

A view from the abandoned public bathhouse.

Igor
Lyman

I wasn't going to send any photo. But when Yana said I had to, I chose this one. So here's its story:

Due to the Russian occupation it's been more than 4 years since I've seen my Sea of Azov and my Berdyansk. During these years, wherever I go, I want to visit a beach. And I write the name of my native port city in Ukrainian on the sand. I did the same thing, by the way, on the beach in Sydney, where Yana and I ended up thanks to Tim.

I took this photo on the day when Tim and Neil held a workshop about visual storytelling. I took it on the Spanish island of Ibiza, where the delegation of Berdyansk State Pedagogical University signed a cooperation agreement with University of the Balearic Islands a few days ago. I took a photo of the inscription "Berdyansk" on the beach in Ibiza from several angles. But I chose one where the horizon with other islands is not visible, so the sand and sea waves are almost indistinguishable from those dear to my heart in Berdyansk.

Alla
Melnychuk

The photo captures the story of my first encounter with the participatory theatre performance The First Performance for children aged 0 to 3.

It was my first time attending a performance created for babies.

Yana
Sychikova

Elvis the cat knows: the appearance of this suitcase means his mom will disappear in a few hours. She sometimes disappears even without the suitcase, but then she comes back quickly. Sometimes he doesn't even notice it. With the suitcase, she disappears for a long time. Lately, more and more often.

When she returns, she brings unfamiliar smells. He needs to double-check whether there's the scent of another cat. It annoys him that she carries her things in a suitcase. Why doesn't she take a cardboard box? A bag? He has always known that humans are foolish—his mom too.

Anastasiia
Fedorchenko

This week was very special for me, because I climbed Mount Konyk for the first time — 700 metres high. In the first photo, I am simply smiling sincerely in the forest — right at the beginning, when I still had plenty of energy and a good mood. Then there is a photo where I am taking pictures of the students from above. There were so many of them, and it looked truly impressive and atmospheric. After that, there is just the forest, which really calmed me down, and the spring where we drank water — it was very cold and delicious. And the last photo shows my lunch, which felt incredibly tasty after the climb.

It was a little difficult, but I am very glad I did it. Now this is one of those days I will definitely remember.

Anastasiia
Fedorchenko

a continuation...

Daryna
Smyshliaieva

The way home

The way home is not about kilometres. It is about the way your heart starts beating faster when you see a familiar turn. The wet hood of an old car after the rain reminds you of your father's words — that it will still serve for a long time. The nectarine tree by the gate, covered in pink blossom, was planted by your mother last spring, simply to make the place more beautiful. In the car mirror, you see yourself wearing glasses and smiling, because you know that very soon someone will hug you. A little goat in the yard seems to remember you from childhood. Tulips in a glass on the kitchen table — your mother put them there especially for you. The cat, waiting under the soft light in your room. A dear little child who is already beginning to put letters together into the word “aunt.” The path along the Kakhovka Reservoir, where you used to walk with your grandfather when you were little. The park with a long alley, where your father took you every summer. The way home is not just a road. It is a return to who you are when no one is watching. To the smell of borshch, to your mother's voice, to the silence of your parents' home.

You do not simply arrive. You return to yourself.

Daryna
Smyshliaieva

a continuation...

Daryna
Smyshliaieva

a continuation...

Alina
Kuchynska

... This week became a true symphony of my everyday life, where every note had its own special shade. It all began with a deep dive into intellectual depths, where I persistently worked through pages of notes, absorbing new knowledge. Later, my rhythm changed and became much faster, as I had to manage everything while still keeping confidence in every step. In the middle of this whirlwind of tasks, I found a moment for beauty: the tulips I received were not just a bright accent, but a small reminder of the tenderness of spring. The official atmosphere of an open event at work added significance to my achievements and allowed me to feel my professional growth.

And the final chord of each day was the warm embrace of my kitten, whose purring is the best therapy for the soul.

Nazar
Mulchenko

Deepless sky

When you look down, you see the limit.

When you look straight, you catch a distant border with your eyes.

But when you look up, you observe something unachievable — the infinity.

Nazar
Mulchenko

Deepless sky

Spring has finally awoken and now it is covering itself with green leafy garment, embroidered with blossoming fruits.

Seems to me this summer will be “cherrish” and pleasantly sweet.

Nazar
Mulchenko

Deepless sky

Every morning as a part of my routine I go for a walk with my lovely dog Monica.

We both admire the view of the landscape, the slowly rising solar disc and the mist, which is a rare natural phenomenon in my town.

Karyna
Bryniuk

This week is about searching for light in the ever-changing flow of everyday life. It is a story about the fleeting nature of time and the elusive beauty of the moments “in between.” The story begins with spring blossoms on a grey street. Then come dramatic sunsets, gradually flowing into a mystical, slightly blurred night atmosphere under the cold glow of the moon. At dawn, there is a play of sunlight through glass, and the final moment is the absolute carefreeness of a black cat warming itself on a car.

No matter how the days change from light to darkness, it is always worth finding a moment to simply stop and enjoy the calm.

Karyna
Bryniuk

a continuation...

